

**INNOVATIONS AND ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN
TEACHING ECONOMIC SCIENCES SCIENCES**

Samarkand state university architecture and construction

Musurmanov Radjab.Maxammatovich.

Komilova Mukammal Shavkatovna.

This article develops scientifically based proposals and recommendations on innovations and advanced foreign experience in teaching economic sciences, their characteristics, and the importance of teaching methods and technologies in foreign countries.

Key words: Economics, educational and methodological complexes, advanced pedagogical technologies, information technologies, electronic textbooks, multimedia, problem-based lectures.

When we talk about the issue of education, which is the most important condition for raising a mature generation and a generation with high intellectual potential in our country, we often talk more about strengthening the material and technical base of the industry, building new schools, lyceums and colleges, higher educational institutions, and modernizing them. . Because they fundamentally change the content and quality of education.

Cultivation of qualified personnel meeting the requirements of the world market has become an urgent issue of our time. It is worth noting that the concept of the production category in the national model of personnel training is the main customer, who determines the need for personnel in production, as well as the requirements for the quality of their training, and appears as a participant in the process of providing the personnel training system in terms of financial and material technology. The high qualification of specialists and the increase of their

creativity can be realized only due to scientific and innovative activities. If, in order to implement their ideas and scientific directions, they produce marketable products or provide services, and if they involve young specialists and students in this process, productive and effective results can be achieved. This, in turn, provides opportunities to meet their life needs through intellectual work as an integration of the educational process, scientific and industrial environment. That's why learning to finance one's mental work as much as possible, moving to the order of advancement, is becoming the need of the hour.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" fully reveal the essence of the process of raising a competent person and qualified specialist. Teaching "Economics" with the help of modern pedagogical technologies is of great importance in the implementation of the tasks provided for in these legal documents.

It envisages the implementation of tasks such as improving and further developing the personnel training system, further strengthening the resources, personnel and information bases of educational institutions, fully providing the educational process with new educational and methodological complexes, advanced pedagogical technologies, and informatization of the educational process. In the implementation of these tasks, teachers working in the higher education system are required to have high professional skills, computer literacy and the ability to know foreign languages.

In this process, several problems of advanced pedagogical technologies are solved. That is:

- resource, personnel and information bases of educational institutions will be further strengthened;
- the educational process is fully provided with new educational and methodological obligations, advanced pedagogical technologies;

- determination and development of national (elite) higher education institutions is carried out;
- independent functioning of vocational education institutions and forms of self-management will be strengthened;
- informatization of the educational process, the continuous education system will be fully covered by the computer information network connecting to the global information network.

In accordance with the state and social order placed before the continuous education system, higher educational institutions increase the efficiency of the educational process, by introducing the latest achievements of science into practice, create creative, socially active, highly spiritual, professional, loyal to the Motherland, national and universal people. It is intended to fulfill important tasks such as bringing up a well-rounded person who is brought up in the spirit of values, who can think creatively and independently, who feels his duty and responsibility before the state and society, and inculcates the idea of national independence into his mind and heart.

In the process of educational work, it is important to teach students to think creatively, to adapt to changing situations, to organize activities based on free competition, and to be able to use information technologies, electronic textbooks and multimedia in practical training. This requires the education of students' independence, free thinking, analysis of educational activities, professional skills and computer literacy should be turned into their internal needs in the future.

Before talking about innovations and advanced foreign experiences in teaching "Marketing", let's talk about what innovation and advanced foreign experiences are:

The concept of innovation is derived from the English language, "innavation", which means innovation.

Advanced foreign experiences are scientific and practical knowledge and experiences gained over the years in the field of Economy. The use of multimedia systems in the application of such experiences to the educational process is a guarantee of achieving high efficiency.

Multimedia (multi-many, media-environment) is a field of computer technology related to the use of information in different physical forms (text, graphics, pictures, sound, animation, video, etc.) available in different carriers.

Multimedia is a set of hardware and software that allows a person to communicate with a computer using sound, video, graphics, text, and animation.

Modern pedagogical technologies are a set of new forms, methods and tools of the educational process, which are integrated into one system based on scientific-theoretical and methodological basis. In this case, the integrity of the goal, task, activity and pedagogical result is ensured in the combination of new content, form, method and means, and the educational process that guarantees the achievement of educational goals is designed and implemented. The technological approach is, first of all, not a description, but a practical instructional structure that allows the realization of the designed results.

The conditions that determine the quality of education related to the educational process are as follows:

- teaching at a high scientific-pedagogical level;
- writing problem reports;
- interesting organization of lessons in question-and-answer style;
- use of advanced pedagogical technologies and multimedia guides;
- to put in front of students the problems that encourage and make them think;
- demand;
- individual work with students;
- encourage creativity;

- teaching to communicate freely, to think creatively;
- involvement in scientific research and other activities ensure the priority of education.

Consideration of these aspects in the teaching of economic sciences plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process.

REFERENCES:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Ш.М.Мирзиёевнинг 2019 йил 8 октябрдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикаси олий таълим тизимини 2030 йилгача ривожлантириш концепциясини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида”ги ПФ-5847-сонли Фармони.
2. М.Хошимова, Д.Файзуллаева. “Замонавий таълим ва инновацион технологиялар бўйича илғор хорижий тажрибалар” модули бўйича ЎЎМ., БИММ, 2015 й.
3. Буриев Х.Т., Усмонов И.А., Комилова М.Ш.. Маркетинг. Дарслик. -Т.: СамДАҚУ, 2022.-256 б.
4. Х.Т.Бuriyev, М.Ш. Komilova Qurilishda menejment. Darslik. SAMDAQU, 2022.-276 б.
5. Komilova Mukammal Shavkatovna Abdixoliqov Jamshid Abdixalilovich. "USE OF MARKETING STRATEGY AS A FACTOR OF INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.3 (2023).
6. Komilova, M. Sh. "O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYA SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI." *Евразийский журнал академических*

исследований 2.3 (2022): 575-584.

7. Sh, Komilova M. "RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING TIZIMLI RIVOJLANISHIDA BOSHQARUV USLUBLARINING O'RNI." *Journal of marketing, business and management* 1.5 (2022): 53-57.

8. Жуманов, Ш. Н., М. Ш. Комилова, and А. Х. Ташимов. "“МАРКЕТИНГ” ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШДАГИ ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВА ИЛҒОР ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ." *Экономика и социум* 4-1 (107) (2023): 586-589.

9. Komilova, Mukammal Shavkatovna, and Jamshid Abdikhalilovich Abdikholikov. "THE ROLE OF EMPLOYEES IN ENSURING THE LABOR POTENTIAL OF ENTERPRISES." *Academic research in educational sciences* 3.11 (2022): 481-484.

10. Shavkatovna, Komilova Mukammal, and Shernazarov Temurbek Tulkinovich. "IMPROVEMENT OF ACTIVITIES OF HOUSING AND UTILITIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN." *World Bulletin of Management and Law* 22 (2023): 25-27.

11. Shavkatovna, Komilova Mukammal, and Abdixoliqov Jamshid Abdixalilovich. "THE ROLE OF EMPLOYEES IN ENSURING THE LABOR POTENTIAL OF ENTERPRISES." *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI* 2.12 (2022): 135-137.

12. Musakulovna, Rakhmonova Feruza, Komilova Mukammal Shavkatovna, and Shernazarov Temurbek Tulkinovich. "USE OF MARKETING CONCEPTS IN THE ACTIVITY OF ORGANIZATIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF FORMING AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY." *World Economics and Finance Bulletin* 17 (2022): 55-56.

13. Shavkatovna, Komilova Mukammal, and Olimova Lola Erkinovna. "WAYS OF EFFICIENT USE OF LABOR RESOURCES IN THE COUNTRY." *World Economics and Finance Bulletin* 7 (2022): 85-90.

1. Buriev, Khakim, Ravshan Kurbanov, and Maruf Rayimov. "PRODUCTION AND TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES IN CONSTRUCTION." *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology* 3.6 (2023): 1521-1525.

2. Буриев, Х. Т., and И. А. Усманов. "ПОВЫШЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН." *Россия: тенденции и перспективы развития* 17-1 (2022): 363-371.

3. Буриев, Х. Т., and И. А. Усманов. "Пути совершенствования организационно-экономического механизма повышения качества строительства: монография." (2020).

4. Буриев, Хаким Тошимович, and Ильхом Ачилович Усманов. "A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation." *Недвижимость: экономика, управление* 4 (2021): 70-74.

5. Усманов, И. А., and Х. Т. Буриев. "Пути совершенствования стимулирования повышения качества работ в сельском строительстве." *Часопис економічних реформ* 4 (2017): 25-30.